

SciAuth Student Fellows Project Report:
An Introduction to Token-Based Authentication

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1. What is Authentication?

Imagine you've just received a brand-new iPhone as a gift. Eager to try it out, you decide to indulge in a little retail therapy with Amazon on the new phone. You downloaded Amazon, fill your virtual cart with everything you want to buy, but before you could checkout, the site stops you with a prompt: "Enter your username and password to log in."

This simple combination of username and password is the most popular authentication mechanism and is the cornerstone of digital security. It's Amazon's way of ensuring that the person trying to access your account and purchase products with the credit card on file is actually you. Suppose Amazon only asks for your username, but not your password, then anyone with your username can access your account and even order items using your funds. This authentication method is based on the premise that you are the only one who knows the password of your account. As this premise sometimes fails, Amazon also provides two-factor authentication (2FA) that sends a verification code to your phone which you need to fill out when logging in. Since the person who knows your username, password, and has your phone is more likely to be you, this two-factor authentication adds another layer of security to your account.

For those with a Microsoft or Google email account, have you ever encountered the situation where an iOS app allows you to sign in with Microsoft or Google? Suppose you are signing into a time-management iOS application that offers Microsoft and Google sign-in options. After you choose the sign-in option via Microsoft or Google, a page from the company pops out, you fill out the password for the account, and you are signed in. This is a prime example of cross-platform authentication at work. By choosing to sign in with Microsoft or Google, you are giving the task of authenticating your identity from the app you're signing in to Microsoft or Google.

As you may realize, authentication is being used everywhere in our digital world. So, what exactly is authentication? According to [\[Microsoft Security\]](#), "authentication is the process that companies use to confirm that only the right people, services, and apps with the right permission can get organizational resources." Amazon uses username, password, and verification code to make sure that only you, or someone you gave access to your account, can view purchase history or checkout. For those apps using cross-platform authentication, they are making sure that only someone who can verify their Microsoft or Google account can know, for example, the detail information on a time-management app.

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2. Cookies VS. Token Based Authorization

On Amazon, a user can browse different items even if the user is not logged in. However, the user can only access the shopping cart or the checkout page after logging in. This mechanism of controlling what the user is authorized to access is called access control or authorization. It determines who is allowed to access certain data, apps, and resources, and in what circumstances [[Microsoft Security](#)]. In the Amazon scenario, whether the user can access cart or checkout depends on the circumstances of whether the user is logged in.

How can the Amazon server know what circumstances the users are in? It uses session cookies to store authentication data. After the user is authenticated, the Amazon server generates and sends cookies, containing information like the fortune cookies containing a note, to the web browser. The web browser stores the cookies they receive for a predetermined period of time and attaches the relevant cookies to any future requests the user makes of the web browser, such as a request to access the cart. The Amazon server keeps track of active sessions in the database, while the browser holds the identifier to the active session. When requesting to access a new web page, such as the cart page, the session ID is used to look up information about the user's privileges for accessing the cart page in the database [[Cloudflare](#); [okta Developer](#)].

The user sends login request

The user sends new request (with a cookie)

Figure 1. A server tracks a user's session using cookies [[GeeksforGeeks](#)].

Besides cookies, tokens are another common way to store information about the user's session. Like cookies, the user sends the token to the web server with every new request, so that the web server can check if the token is valid and authorize the request accordingly [[Geeks for Geeks](#)]. We'll expand on tokens' structure and different types of tokens later.

The user sends login request

Figure 2. A server authorizes access using a token [\[GeeksforGeeks\]](#)

3. Authorization via OAuth 2.0 Authorization Framework

According to [\[RFC 6749\]](#), “the OAuth 2.0 authorization framework enables a third-party application to obtain limited access to an HTTP service”. For example, going back to our iOS time-management application example, the app might want to access the calendar in your Microsoft account after you login through your Microsoft account, so that it can show how many hours you spend on meetings per week. So, we want the application to access calendar, but we probably don’t want it to access our emails because of sensitive information. Before OAuth 2.0, the application will retain the login information of your Microsoft account when you sign in through Microsoft to access information on your Microsoft account. This traditional client-server authentication model poses a significant risk that the application can access everything on your account. OAuth 2.0 jumps in to solve this problem. Instead, it only grants the third-party application (the iOS app) access to limited HTTP service to access information on your Microsoft account. OAuth 2.0 follows the authorization code flow illustrated below.

Authorization Code Flow (RFC 6749, 4.1)

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Figure 3. A user grants authorization using the OAuth 2.0 Authorization Code Flow [Medium]

I know the chart above looks very complicated, but let's dissect the different components in this graph together. There are four parties involved in this graph: resource owner, client, authorization server, and resource server.

- Resource owner: the person that's using the application.
- Client: the application (the time management application)
- Authorization server: server that authenticates user's identity and issue access token (Microsoft Identity Platform)
- Resource server: server hosting the protected resources (Microsoft)

According to [RFC 6749], instead of using the resource owner's credentials (e.g., username and password) to access protected resources, OAuth 2.0 elaborates that the application obtains an access token – "a string denoting a specific scope, lifetime, and other access attributes". This token is issued to the application by the authorization server, and the application uses the access token to access the protected resources hosted by the resource server [RFC 6749].

In our example, the user can grant the time-management app (client) access to her protected schedule stored on the Microsoft account (resource server), without sharing the username and password of the Microsoft account with the app. Instead, the user authenticates directly with the Microsoft Identity Platform (authorization server) that's trusted by the Microsoft account, which issues the time-management app access token. With the access token, the application can make HTTP request to Microsoft for user's calendar, and Microsoft will talk to the Microsoft Identity Platform to make sure the access token is valid. If valid, Microsoft returns the requested resource to the application.

4. Understanding Tokens in Authorization

Tokens play a crucial role in the authorization process, so let's understand the different types of tokens and their respective roles in the authorization process. We are going to elaborate on access token, refresh token, and ID token.

a. Access Token

As talked about in previous paragraphs, access tokens are credentials used to access protected resources from the resource server. It is a string representing an authorization issued to the client, like a student ID card that can grant you access to dorms, gyms, the pool, etc. However, access token is opaque to the client, but can be understood by resource server. We discuss opaque tokens in more detail in Section 6.

b. Refresh Token

According to [\[RFC 6749\]](#), “refresh tokens are credentials used to obtain access tokens”. Since access tokens can expire or become invalid, the authorization server issues refresh tokens to the client to obtain a new access token. This token is opaque to the client.

This diagram illustrates when and how access tokens and refresh tokens are used.

Figure 4. Refreshing an Expired Access Token [\[RFC 6749\]](#)

c. ID Token

An ID token includes details about a user's authentication event and is meant for the OAuth client to read. It might also hold personal information about the user, like their name or email address, so that the client can use that information in the application [\[OAuth.net\]](#).

5. JWT – JSON Web Token as Access Token, Refresh Token, and ID Token

According to [\[JWT.io\]](https://jwt.io), “JSON Web Token (JWT) is an open-standard (RFC 7519) that defines a compact and self-contained way for securely transmitting information between parties as a JSON object”. Upon successfully authenticating the user’s credentials, the authorization server needs to send the user’s details to the client. To transmit that information efficiently, the authorization server sends a JWT to the client that encapsulates the user’s details, among other information. JWT consist of three parts separated by dots “.”, which are header, payload, and signature. It looks something like this:

xxxxx.yyyyy.zzzzz

We will focus on the payload of the JWT. For more information on header and signature, go to [JWT.io](https://jwt.io).

Payload, which is the second part of the JWT, contains the claims. For example, below shows a typical JSON payload sent by authorization server Google when signing in an app with Google:

```
{
  "iss": "https://accounts.google.com",
  "azp": "407408718192.apps.googleusercontent.com",
  "aud": "407408718192.apps.googleusercontent.com",
  "sub": "115184802996457052527",
  "email": "xyz@gmail.com",
  "email_verified": true,
  "at_hash": "TL13lxHYueIRkFqn88HuUQ",
  "name": "xyz",
  "picture":
  "https://lh3.googleusercontent.com/a/ACg8ocIKnNd0hjDN5XD8W1PyS3vBHe5briKQI_0u_RK
  gvnif_QRiRQ=s96-c",
  "given_name": "xy",
  "family_name": "z",
  "iat": 1712282087,
  "exp": 1712285687
}
```

- iss: who created and signed the token
- azp and aud: Client IDs issued by Google Identity Platform for the application.
- sub: the user’s Google user ID
- email: the user’s email
- email_verified: indicates the email associated with the account is verified
- at-hash: the hash value of access token
- name: the user’s name
- picture: points to the image of the user’s profile

- given_name: given name of the user
- family_name: family name of the user
- iat: issued at (seconds since Unix epoch)
- exp: expiration time (seconds since Unix epoch)

Then, this JSON is Base64Url encoded to form the second part of the JWT, the yyyyy in our previous example [\[JWT.io\]](#). In authentication, when the user logs in using their credentials, a JWT will be returned by the authorization server to the client. Whenever the user wants to access a protected resource, the client should send the JWT, typically in the Authorization header in HTTP request. The resource server will then check if the JWT is valid with the authorization server, and if so, grants access to the protected resource [\[JWT.io\]](#).

6. Opaque Token

a. Opaque Token in Microsoft Authentication

To better understand token-based authorization in iOS application using Microsoft sign-in, I followed the [Tutorial: Sign in users and call Microsoft Graph from an iOS or macOS app](#) to create an iOS app in Swift. After completing the code, I tried to print the access token issued by Microsoft Identity Platform as a log message so that I can better its structure. However, no matter what approaches I used, the printed access token was not a JWT separated by three dots “.”, but more like a random string. Below is an example of the generated string.

```
“EwBoA8l6BAAUbdBa3x2OMJElkF7gJ4z/VbCPEz0AARfD4UXcX2JrSKOyOIshTJ6xhngV
VWDGOyoKCRkVcsZwMhfjh0HHV ...”
```

After discussing with Jim Basney, my mentor for this [\[SciAuth\]](#) project, I learned that this was an opaque token. According to [\[Cloudentity\]](#), “the opaque token is a random unique string of character issued by the authorization server”. It is one of the possible formats that access token or refresh token can take. It lacks information that could identify the user, thereby preventing both the client and the resource server from accessing it. Consequently, the resource server needs to call the authorization server and request the token introspection because the opaque token contains an identifier to information stored on the authorization server. In this sense, it is like a pointer to the access token. This adds another layer of security (privacy). The access tokens are intended for the resource server, usually opaque to the client [\[RFC 6749\]](#). Nevertheless, the client might violate the rule and parse a token. By using opaque token, clients are prevented from implementing logic based on the content of access tokens [\[Curity\]](#).

b. Opaque Token in Google Authentication

After inquiring about authentication in Microsoft sign-in, I was curious about Google authentication on an iOS application using Google sign-in. So, I followed the tutorial [Get Started with Google Sign-In for iOS and macOS](#), and forked an example Google SignIn-iOS application from this GitHub repository [\[GitHub\]](#) that is linked in the tutorial. I then tried to print the access token and discovered that the printed result was not a JWT. Instead, it has the example format as the following, which looks like a meaningless string like the previous opaque token from Microsoft iOS application.

“ya29.a0Ad52N39aJBE7T6Lr5EbHHLIsv0DJVZ2-dth7lPSYQZrcaKgdlDs9lXek5-UyM0rVK7hU7YnnyvndQJQqOWNcDMMYozI7hJU4Qn4-...”

After logging in and out and calling the Google API multiple times to get multiple access tokens, I noticed that even though the printed access tokens were not identical, they all had the prefix of “ya29” [[jpassing](#)]. After some research, I found that the prefix “ya29” is common among all Google-issued access token. Beyond the prefix shared among all Google-issued access tokens, the access tokens are opaque tokens, just like the access token issued by Microsoft Identity Platform.

7. Security Considerations with Token-Based Authorization

Even though OAuth is a flexible and extensible framework, its security considerations depend on many factors. Below illustrates the security considerations in the client app, the authorization endpoint, and the token endpoint from [[RFC 6819](#)].

a. Security Considerations in Client Application

In the client application, attackers usually target information of user credentials, access and refresh tokens, personal data like email, address, and payment information. A common tactic used by attackers involves redirecting users to malicious websites through compromised redirect URLs, where users can be deceived into providing personal information or credentials (phishing attacks). With the obtained credentials, a malicious client can impersonate another client and obtain access to protected resource if the impersonated client can't keep the credentials confidential. To add another layer of security to this type of attack, we can use two-factor authentication to further authenticate the user, as the start of this report discussed.

Besides user credentials of username and password, access tokens also need to be kept confidential in transit between authorization server, resource server, and the client. Therefore, RFC 6749 elaborates that the client app should request access tokens with the minimal scope necessary, which is also the reason why some access tokens are opaque.

b. Security Considerations in Authorization Endpoint and Token Endpoint

For the authorization endpoint and token endpoint, man-in-the middle attacks can occur when an attacker intercepts the communication between the application and the authorization server, capturing user's credentials, authorization code, or the access token. To prevent man-in-the-middle attacks from happening, OAuth 2.0 standards dictate that the authorization server must set up a secure, encrypted connection to communicate with the client. This secure connection is known as TLS, which stands for Transport Layer Security. TLS is like a protected tunnel for your data to keep out anyone who shouldn't be listening in. Every time the client app communicates with the authorization server for authorization code or access token, it should make sure that the server is the one it claims to be. To accomplish this, the client should check the server's TLS certificate, just like when we check someone's ID to make sure they are who they claim to be.

8. Conclusions

In conclusion, this report has demonstrated the important role of token-based authentication in ensuring secure interactions between users and platforms. The evolution of authentication methods, from simple passwords to the OAuth 2.0 framework, has been a significant step forward in managing access rights without compromising user credentials.

We also discussed the difference of access, refresh, and ID tokens and their function in controlling resource access while maintaining user privacy. The examples of opaque tokens utilized by Microsoft and Google have highlighted the security benefits of this approach, preventing unauthorized client-side access to information about the user.

Last but not least, we also went through the significance of implementing the principle of least privilege in token-based authorization and the crucial role of secure communication channels like TLS in mitigating potential security risks.

I hope you've enjoyed this dive into token-based authentication as much as I have. I would like to extend my gratitude to my mentor, Jim Basney, for the invaluable guidance, and to the SciAuth Student Fellowship for their support along this journey.

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